

Assessing the Pali Canon as the only evidence to what the Buddha thought

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Abstract

This article explores the scholarly shift from traditional Buddhist texts to inscriptions as a more reliable source. While acknowledging the value of inscriptions due to their known origin and potential dating, the focus narrows to Asoka's inscriptions as the only ones relevant to Pali canonical material. It contends that non-Buddhist texts lack credible references to the Buddha within half a millennium of his life. Despite uncertainties, some references to Buddhist ideas, influencing Brahminical thought post-Buddha, carry an authentic air. The study suggests positive and negative impacts, including the intriguing possibility of Bhagavad-Gita passages responding to Buddhism, though the origin remains ambiguous.

Key Words: Buddhism, Pali canon

Introduction

In recent times some scholars of Buddhism have decried the value of texts and turned to inscriptions. Inscriptions are texts too, to be more veridical than other texts. Inscriptions do have the advantage that we usually know where they come from, and sometimes they are also dated or at least roughly datable. So of course we should make full use of them. However, the only inscriptions which can have any bearing at all on the Pali canonical material are those of Asoka.

There are no references to the Buddha in non-Buddhist texts which can plausibly be dated to less than half a millennium after he lived. There are some references to Buddhist ideas probably impossible to date with any accuracy but nevertheless carry an air of authenticity. Buddhist ideas began to exert an influence on Brahminical ideas not very long after his death. Just as is the case

with the influence of earlier ideas on the Buddha himself, some influence was positive, amounting to tacit acceptance, while much of it was negative. It has been very plausibly argued, for example, that there are famous passages in the *Bhagavad Gita* which are framed as a reply to Buddhism.¹ However, there is nothing in these non-Buddhist texts to show that the influences to which they are responding emanate from the Buddha himself rather than from his followers in later generations.

For information on what the Buddha said and did we are thus dependent on the Buddhist texts, the Canon. There is a complete version of this Canon in the Pali language, the great majority of texts in this version survive also in Chinese translation, some of them in more than one version. The Chinese translations were made from Indian languages, but most of them probably not from Pali. One substantial part of the canon, the Vinaya, has survived not merely in four Chinese versions but in a Buddhist Sanskrit version and a Tibetan version closely related to it. Very few of the old Suttas were translated into Tibetan. So, although the Tibetan Buddhist canon, known as the *Kanjur*, is vast, its importance for evaluating the earlier canon is negligible.

A few manuscripts containing versions of *suttas* found in the Pali Canon survive in other Indian languages. Most of these have been discovered quite recently in the area known in ancient times as Gandhara, which stretched from the Kabul Valley in the west to the Indus Valley in the east. These may date from the second century AD and thus be the oldest Buddhist manuscripts ever found. Scholars are currently working on them. However, these new finds will have no effect on our view of the Buddha and his ideas. Scholars are much given to emphasizing how important it is to compare the Pali versions of canonical *suttas* with other extant versions, whether they be Gandharan manuscripts or Chinese translations. The first to agree that having all this material to hand in a form which makes comparison easy should be a top priority of Buddhist scholarship. But it is easy (to convey a misleading impression of what such comparisons have so far achieved. True, literally thousands of differences between versions come to light. But an overwhelming majority of these differences, so far at least, have been rather trivial. Texts are differently arranged, both with regard to each other and internally. The locations at which the Buddha is said to have delivered specific sermons are very often different. One thing that has struck is that when a Pali expression is obscure to us, the Chinese version tends to omit it. One also finds that doctrinal lists tend to be slightly longer in the Chinese.

The Pali version of Suttas and Vinaya stands unrivalled as our oldest evidence, and if we are seriously interested in how Buddhism began, and hence in how it developed². How did these documents originate and how well have they survived the passing of time? Most of the Pali manuscripts that survive in Sri Lanka and Burma were copied as late as the eighteenth and

nineteenth centuries. In northern Thailand, there are many manuscripts dating back to the sixteenth century. In Burma in the twelfth century, grammarians systematized Pali grammar and prosody, thus exercising considerable influence on how the language was written thereafter, both in Burma and elsewhere. However, analysis of the only Pali manuscript to antedate those grammarians shows a language identical in most respects to that preserved by the later manuscripts. This oldest witness consists of four leaves of a canonical text; it is in Kathmandu and scholars have dated it to c. 800 AD. It seems, however, to have been copied from a north Indian original some centuries older³.

This may give the impression that our evidence for the readings in Pali canonical texts is alarmingly modern. Does this impugn their reliability? Scholarship has not yet advanced far enough to give a full answer to this question. There are vast numbers of manuscripts of the Canon, especially of the Suttas, but so far as we are still quite unclear about how many archetypes the extant manuscripts are derived from and when those archetypes are likely to date from. It is some consolation that most of the text is supported by two kinds of testimonial: firstly, an enormously high percentage of the text is repeated and found in more than one place in the Canon, and secondly, very much of the text is quoted in commentaries and sub-commentaries. Of course, once a text is corrupted, misguided scribes may carry the corruption over into parallel texts. The situation is far from satisfactory. Still, we must remember that we are worried here about points of detail, not about whether whole texts and doctrines have been added or changed.

According to the Pali chronicles of Sri Lanka, the Canon as a whole was first committed to writing in Sri Lanka in the first century BC⁴. It is reasonable to assume that some texts may have been written down earlier in India or Sri Lanka, but exactly in what language we cannot know. The act of writing down the Canon presumably played a part in stabilizing it, particularly as it drew a line between what counted as canonical and what did not⁵. There are a few texts which at various times and places have been either included or excluded from the Canon, but this is not the case with any of the Suttas or Vinaya rules.

Whatever the precise date at which the Pali canonical texts were first written down, what matters most to the historian who wishes to find the Buddha is to what extent he thinks he can trust the transmission of material before that date. To put it slightly differently, when were these texts composed, and do we have anything like the original compositions?

The texts that record the Buddha's sermons are for the most part narrations in which the Buddha plays the leading role, though in some cases the sermon is ascribed to a leading monk. The tradition holds that the texts of the sermons were formulated at the meeting which the monks

held soon after the Buddha's death. This meeting is known in English as 'the First Council'⁶, but the term translated 'council' really means 'communal recitation'. The *Suttas* were first recited, in response to questioning, by Ananda, the monk who had been the Buddha's personal attendant during the latter half of his forty-five-year preaching career. The *Vinaya* similarly recited by Upali, had presumably been present at all the early ordination ceremonies. When Upali and Ananda formulated the texts, they were rehearsed by all the monks attending the council, thus beginning the tradition of oral preservation of the teachings.

Each Buddhist tradition preserves its own version of exactly what happened at this First Council and there is little agreement on who did what or other details. It is quite clear that, even if we confine ourselves to what we are calling for convenience 'the early canonical texts' these were not all created in their present form at the First Council. A few sermons even mention people who are known to have lived after the Buddha. The *Vinaya Khandhaka* concludes with the Second Council, which is alleged to have taken place a hundred years after the First; about sixty years is probably closer to the correct figure⁷, but in the present context the discrepancy is not important.

On the other hand, the texts which were recited at the First Council - whichever they were - must have had some kind of existence before that. There is an episode recorded in the Canon⁸ in which the Buddha asks a young monk whom he is meeting for the first time to tell him some *Dhamma*; the monk recites the whole *Atthaka-vagga* (a section of the *Sutta-nipata*) and the Buddha commends him. The text does not say who originally composed the poems of the *Atthaka-vagga*; it could be the Buddha himself; it could be the young monk's teacher, Mahakaccana, who was a reputed preacher; it could be yet other monks; and it could be a combination of these since not all the poems need be by the same author.

The body of sermons preserved in Pali is very large: the Buddhists themselves count them as 17,505⁹ a greater number than appears to have come down to us. Most of them are short, and the corpus is full of repetitions and redundancies. Even so, it is a massive body of literature, mainly in prose. Either at the outset or very early on, the body of sermons was divided into four collections and monks and nuns specialized in learning by heart one of the collections (or another part of the Canon) in order to preserve it.

Since in the time of the Buddha, there was no writing, a set of words could only have assumed the status of a 'text' - for example, of a *Sutta* - once someone had decided to create such a fixed entity, memorized it, and in due course passed it on to others for them to memorize in their turn. The Buddha's First Sermon can stand as an example of what I mean. It is generally known as 'Setting in Motion the Wheel of the Teaching' (*Dhamma-cakka-pavattana*), but this title is not found before the commentaries. It was delivered to five disciples who became the first five monks

to alter the Buddha himself. No doubt some or all of them who were present on that occasion remembered what the Buddha talked about. This probably blended in memory with what he 'should' have talked about to introduce others to the insight he had had which constituted his Enlightenment, a self-authenticating experience.

The first topic in the *Sutta* is the Middle Way between indulging and mortifying the flesh, which is the way that leads to Enlightenment; this fits the biographical narrative very well. Logically one could also argue the oilier way round: that the biographical narrative was shaped to fit the First Sermon; but this is such an uneconomical explanation, which leads to many complications, that it is highly improbable. The Middle Way is briefly stated, not expounded in any detail, and is then said to be the same as the Noble Eightfold Path. The Noble Eightfold Path is, however, a very different concept, more precisely articulated than a lifestyle which finds the happy medium between indulgence and asceticism. Its eight constituents, from 'right views' to 'right concentration', are then listed. In no case is there a word of explanation of what is meant by 'right'. So what we have been given so far is just headings, not content.

The Buddha now enunciates the Four Noble Truths. Each is first given its name or title and then briefly expanded. K. R. Norman has published an article¹⁰ which demonstrates on purely linguistic grounds that each Noble Truth is indeed just being introduced by title, so that it appears to be an allusion to something already familiar to the audience, like 'the axis of evil' or the 'shock and awe' policy. The fourth Noble Truth is the Noble Eightfold Path, but nothing is added: the list of eight items is merely repeated.

In sum, the composition of the First Sermon is that the version we have probably dates from as late as the Second Council. Because it is embedded in the *Vinaya Khandhaka* in the account of how the Buddha began his preaching career, there is good reason to think that *that* was composed 'shortly before or after' the Second Council.¹¹ Exactly the same text, still without its later title, is also found near the end of the *Samyutta Nikaya*¹² which makes that collection was not closed until about the same time, perhaps at the Second Council itself. On the other hand, there was an earlier, probably shorter, version, which contained the gist of the present version; and the entire text rested on a memory in the Sangha, quite likely buttressed by the Buddha while he was still alive, that those were the topics he talked about on that occasion.

The Pali Canon is immensely repetitious because it is largely composed of pericopes; this is exactly what one would expect of oral literature. Another feature due to its oral origins is the fondness for numbered lists. Verse often helps one, through its metre, to realize when one has omitted an item, but prose does not, so numbered lists can serve that purpose.

The monks and nuns who composed the texts with the building blocks of pericopes were not all of the highest intelligence, for sometimes they inserted pericopes inappropriately¹³. This is important: it seems to be an undeniable case in which neither the canonical corpus nor the commentarial corpus can be made to yield homogeneous authorial unity; in other words, people who did not fully understand the expression have used it in the creation of canonical texts, and other, later people who did not understand it have given more than one interpretation of it in the commentaries.

So what of the commentaries? In interpreting a canonical text, the first thing one must do is to see what the commentary says about it. But that is not to say that one then suspends all critical judgement and takes inquiry no further, as has unfortunately been the practice of some leading Pali scholars even in recent times.

The commentaries on the Buddha's sermons and the Vinaya are all ascribed to one man, Buddhaghosa, whom we know to have been active in Sri Lanka at the very beginning of the fifth century AD. Buddhaghosa also wrote a huge book, called *The Path to Purity* (Visuddhi-magga), which summarizes Theravada Buddhist doctrine in so masterly a fashion that it has remained authoritative to this day. Sometimes the other commentaries refer to *The Path to Purity* for amplification on a topic whether or not they are all the work of Buddhaghosa, but that is not relevant here. To what extent Buddhaghosa (with possible colleagues) is the author and to what extent he is the editor of the commentaries may never be fully known, but it is beyond dispute that he often explicitly cites older commentaries, mostly written in Sinhala. These have all been lost, but obviously, they take us back earlier than the time of Buddhaghosa himself; one scholar who studied them, E.W. Adikaram,¹⁴ deduced that they were closed in the second century AD. What the evidence seems to show beyond doubt is that they were not closed earlier than that. According to tradition (embedded in those same commentaries), their substance goes back to the First Council and was brought to Sri Lanka in the middle of the third century BC by a group led by Mahinda, son of the emperor Asoka; these were the missionaries who introduced Buddhism into the island. Tradition also holds that when the Canon was written down in Sri Lanka in the first century BC the commentaries were written down too. Whether this is true or not, the commentaries at that stage were probably in Sinhala, the local language.

What emerges from all this is that the Theravadin tradition of exegesis, preserved in the Pali language, claims that it stretches right back from the texts we now have to the time of the Buddha himself, a period of about eight hundred years. I see no reason to consider this implausible. But this is entirely different from positing that over those eight centuries, while the commentaries

were transmitted orally (at least to begin with), translated and edited, nothing of importance was added, lost or otherwise changed. For that there would surely be no parallel recorded in human history. Nor was there any cultural scruple to inhibit changing the commentaries, for they do not have the sanctity of being ascribed to the Buddha himself.

It is not merely legitimate but necessary for the student of the Pali Canon to employ the same alert eye as any other textual critic in order to spot discrepancies. Of course, one must not be hasty in jumping to conclusions: an obscurity or difficulty is not necessarily a discrepancy. One must never forget the editorial principle that it is the difficult reading which is likely to be the original, the easy one an attempt by the tradition to smooth over the difficulty.¹⁵

One sort of relevant discrepancy is when a word or expression in a text sounds odd and seems hard to interpret, but then we find it in another text where it fits the context perfectly; one may then hypothesize that the latter context is the original one and the other is secondary, a later creation.

Sometimes this almost stares you in the face. In some passages, it is transparent that the *Mahaparinibbana Sutta*, the account of the Buddha's last days, juxtaposes earlier and later material. This is one of the few texts of which different recensions, the Pali one and several emanating from other early Buddhist traditions, have been carefully compared,¹⁶ an analysis facilitated by its being the longest of all Suttas. Even without this comparison, however, the Pali text alone has tell-tale incongruities. The account of the Buddha's actual passing away has him first going through the ranked set of meditative States: From the first *jhana* up to the fourth, then through the five 'formless Jhanas' culminating in the extinction of apperception and feeling: a series of nine steps in all. At this point, Ananda says to Anuruddha that the Buddha has passed away (*parinibbuto*). but Anuruddha says not so. The Buddha then retraces all nine steps, going back down to the first Jhana. Then he climbs again, and on leaving the fourth *jhana* he dies. Obviously, onlookers could not tell which meditative state the Buddha was in, so the whole account must be an ideological construct. Or rather, two constructs. It seems we must have in the text before us a combination of two versions of the Buddha's death. Normally one would expect the later version to come second, but in this case, the content makes that impossible, so the simpler version, with just the four *jhanas*, is likely to be the older.

It suffices to recall all the discussions about early Marx and later Marx. In the First Sermon, we have seen, the Buddha spells out the Noble Eightfold Path in terms which the tradition never changes: the final step is Right Concentration, Samma Samadhi. Later it seems he was more given to proposing a threefold sequence: morality, concentration, wisdom. Each is the prerequisite for

the proper development of the next. This appears many times, for example, in the *Maha Parinibbana Sutta*. The ancient commentators therefore had a hard time fitting the three into the eight. They had to say that the first two stages of the Noble Eightfold Path were a kind of preliminary wisdom and that after reaching concentration one comes back to the first two stages to make the wisdom perfect. This may suit the first step, right view, but virtually ignores the second, right intention (*samma samkappa*)¹⁸ which according to this revision should be the climax of the whole career.

The whole attempt to harmonize the two formulations, by eight stages and by three, is contorted and indeed pointless.

By calling the Noble Eightfold Path a path he uses a metaphor which implies that its constituents form a sequent and some formulations of the threefold practice of morality, meditation and wisdom carry the same implication.

Earlier attempts at finding strata in the Canon have been so crude that they have earned the very idea of stratification a bad name. Certainly, this can turn into a wild-goose chase, if one allows some prejudice about what the Buddha must have originally said to run away with one, regardless of logic or evidence. But it is no less absurd to insist *a priori* that stratification is impossible. The form and language of the text have probably been reworked so often that formal criteria are likely to be of very limited use: we must rely on the content.

On some matters, particularly matters of formulation, the Buddha may well have changed his mind. But where two flatly contradictory statements are ascribed to him, we may well be able to reason out that only one is authentic.

But there may also be cases where we can logic which thought must have come first and which later.

Notes :

1. For a fine study of the complex history of these two terms, see soon – il Hwang, *Metaphor and Literalism in Buddhism: The Doctrinal History of Nirvana* (2006).
2. This was apparently forgotten at a very early stage. Because of phonetic similarity, *upādi* in this context was changed to *upadhi*. The latter means ‘basic, foundation’, and in

particular was used to refer to the basis for craving (tonhā). As this made satisfactory sense, no one noticed that there was even a problem with the original terms.

3. G.E.R. Lloyd, *Demystifying Mentalities* (190), pp.20-1.
4. *Kosmogonia Rygwedy. Mysl i netafora [Cosmogony of the Rigveda. Thought and Metaphor]* (2001). My quotations in the following passage, unless indicated otherwise, are drawn from the unpublished draft English version.
5. In theory this should be done at dawn, twilight and dusk. The dawn recitation is the most important.
6. For the next seven paragraphs I am wholly indebted to my friend Professor Joanna Jurewicz of the University of Warsaw: on occasion I even use her words.
7. So, incidentally, is Soma; but to discuss that would take us too far afield.
8. This is the latter part of *Mahābhārata*, book XII.
9. Joanna Jurewicz, 'Prajāpati, the fire and the pancāgni-vidyā' (2004).
10. We recall how the Buddha made an advance in the conscious use of abstractions. The mind is therefore the organ which perceives abstractions. 'Mind' is *manam* and 'ideas' *dhamme*, both here being in the accusative.
11. Patrick Olivelle, *The Early Upanisads* (1998), pp, xxi-xxii, P.8 and note to passage cited.
12. In this sense *mahā-bhūta* is commoner than *bhūta*.
13. SNII, 11-12

14. There is a large collection of *suttas* about casual chains; the *Nidānasamyutta of the Samyutta Nikāya*. Most of them are about the Chain of Dependent Origination, but a few concern the chain of the four foods. The most substantial, with vivid similes, are *suttas* 63 and 64 (-SNII, 98-104).
15. Alexander Wynne, *The Origin of Buddhist Meditatin* (2007). The book is based on his Oxford D.Phil. thesis, 2003.
16. Jurewicz has shown that this is the true meaning of the deceptively simple compound *nāma-rūpa*, literally 'name and form'. See next note.

